

Citation for the Presentation of the 2023 ICPE Medal
to
Dr Pornrat Wattanakasiwich

Associate Professor Dr. Pornrat Wattanakasiwich is awarded the ICPE Medal in recognition of her exceptional and sustained contributions to physics education, leadership, and mentoring at the national and regional levels, with collaborations extending beyond. Over two decades, her dedication, expertise, and leadership have significantly advanced physics education in Thailand and contributed to the global physics education community.

As an Associate Professor at Chiang Mai University and currently serving as Associate Dean for Academic Affairs, Faculty of Science, Dr. Pornrat has led numerous projects to improve physics learning through evidence-based instructional strategies. Her research has focused on conceptual understanding, diagnostic tools, and active learning methodologies, particularly in mechanics and thermodynamics. She has introduced innovative teaching tools such as high-speed video analysis, embedded systems for physics experiments, and image processing techniques, significantly enhancing students' conceptual understanding. She has translated these research findings into practice through national and international workshops, training sessions, and collaborations, significantly shaping the professional development of physics teachers.

Dr. Pornrat has been instrumental in the development of the national physics curriculum in Thailand. As the principal author of IPST's high school physics textbooks, she has shaped physics education across the country, ensuring both clarity and rigor. Her influence extends beyond curriculum design—she has helped develop high-quality teaching materials, research-based instructional strategies, and innovative learning resources that have been widely adopted in schools across Thailand.

Dr. Pornrat's influence extends beyond Thailand through significant contributions to the international physics education community. She has collaborated with educators across Asia, Europe, North America, and Australia on projects enhancing physics teaching globally. Her key international engagements include serving as an Endeavour Research Fellow in Australia, contributing to the Euro-Asian Collaboration for Enhancing STEM Education (EASTEM)

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Erasmus+ project, and collaborating with Teachers College, Columbia University (USA) and the University of São Paulo (Brazil) on STEM and digital skills learning platforms. She has served as the committee of the Thai Young Physicist's Tournament (TYPT) since 2012, transforming it into a nationwide educational movement impacting over 250 high schools, inspiring and mentoring young physicists while fostering problem-solving skills, experimental physics expertise, and teamwork among students. In the International Young Physicist's Tournament (IYPT), she served as Thailand's official representative on the International Organizing Committee from 2018 to 2023 and currently serves on the IYPT Disciplinary Committee. She has also delivered keynote speeches and presentations at major international conferences, including the World Conference on Physics Education (2012), ICPE, APPC, and ULICoSTE, on active learning, video analysis, and AI integration in education. Her pioneering recent work on developing AI ethics-aware chatbots for physics students' research writing and researching physics instructors' acceptance of Generative AI demonstrates her forward-thinking commitment to 21st-century education.

Through her notable achievements and extensive network of collaborations, Associate Professor Pornrat Wattanakasiwich has demonstrated foresight, persistence, and leadership in physics education, values which make her a worthy recipient of the ICPE Medal. The award ceremony took place at the International Conference on Physics Education, 2025 in Ropar, India.

<p>Presenting her research on 'Developing an AI Ethics-Aware Chatbot to Support Physics Students' Research Writing' at the ICPE 2025.</p>	<p>Guest lecturer and physics teacher training workshop in Xayaboury Province, Laos, October 19–23, 2011</p>
<p>Dr. Pornrat, along with the team leaders and IYPT 2013 Team Thailand, taking a photo with Nobel Laureate Prof. Osheroff at the IYPT 2013 competition in Taiwan.</p>	<p>Photos showing active learning activities that stimulate analytical thinking in the Introductory Physics course</p>